

Observation protocol template

1. General information
2. Meeting goal
3. Planned time period of the meeting
4. Real time period of the meeting
5. Attendees
6. Planned meeting agenda
7. Which tools do they use?
8. Are there using micro-practices (depends on the observed meeting / agile practice)?
9. Are rules of respectful communication adhered to?
10. Specific observations regarding the procedure and the organization of the meeting